

The keys to design high mechanical performance of CNTs based polymer composite fibers

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SUMMARY

The mechanical properties as well as micromechanical mechanism of carbon nanotubes based polymer composite fibers have been investigated. The dominating roles affecting mechanical performance of composite fibers were illustrated, which would be beneficial to future high mechanical performance nanocomposites design.

Keywords: carbon nanotubes, polymer, nanocomposites, fiber, Raman

HEADINGS

During the past decade, great efforts have been applied to improve the mechanical performance of carbon nanotubes based polymer composites.[1,2] The main factors affecting the mechanical behaviour of CNTs based polymer composites, including nanotubes dispersion, interfacial adhesion, alignment as well as the volume fraction of nanotubes inside matrix have been fully considered. Unfortunately, in most cases, the mechanical performance of CNTs based composites is still beyond our expectation as a consequence of various uncertainties. Here we fabricate the novel CNTs based polymer composite micro-fiber by liquid submersion method, in which nanotubes acting as continuous reinforcing filler rather than discontinuous one. Polymer type effect on the mechanical properties of CNTs composite fiber is also investigated. Furthermore, on the basis our recent work regarding mechanical behavior of pure SWNTs fiber, [3] the micromechanical mechanism of composite fiber is revealed with the help of in-situ Tensile Raman test. The key parameter dominating the mechanical performance of CNTs composites fiber is highly illustrated, which would guide the future design for high performance of CNTs based composite fiber.

Sub Headings

The plot shown in Figure 1 indicate that high tensile modulus together with large failure strength were achieved for thermoset based (i.g. epoxy resin) and thermoplastic (Polyvinyl alcohol) based composite fibers, respectively. Moreover, the poor mechanical performance is observed for rubbery based composites (i.g. PDMS).

Figure 1 Mechanical performance of carbon nanotubes based various polymer composite fibers

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References

1. Jonathan N. Coleman , Umar Khan, Werner J. Blau, Yurii K. Gun’ko, “Small but strong: A review of the mechanical properties of carbon nanotube–polymer composites”, *Carbon* 44 (2006) 1624–1652.
2. Mohammad Moniruzzaman and Karen I. Winey, “Polymer Nanocomposites Containing Carbon Nanotubes”, *Macromolecules* 2006, 39, 5194-5205.
3. Wenjun Ma, Luqi Liu, Rong Yang, Taihua Zhang , Zhong Zhang, Li Song, Yan Ren, Jun Shen , Zhiqiang Niu, Weiya Zhou, and Sishen Xie, “Monitoring Micromechanical Process in Macroscale Carbon Nanotube Films and Fibers” *Adv. Mater.* In press (2008).